

THE BEGINNING OF ART

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Abstract: We can find a lot of works comparing the spiritual world of the East and the West in the works of Kh. Dostmuhammad. In particular, the author's story "The Road to Silence" was very successful in this regard. Adib gives the following explanation about the history of writing this story: "For many years, I have been influenced by the story "Seven Floors" by the famous Italian writer Dino Bustati. Finally, I freely translated this extraordinary original story and finished the story as a "view" of it. The story is based on the personal views of two polar figures about life and death.

Keywords: art, tragedy, approaches, explain, slave, charms, philosophy, explanation.

People named Dino Korte, the hero of the story "Seven Floors", and Zahid Yaqin, the hero of "The Road to Quiet House". Both of them end up in the hospital with a minor illness. Both hospital buildings have seven floors. Only in the hospital they place Dino Korte on the seventh floor and Zahid Yaqin on the first floor.

In his interpretation, death is a tragedy for a Westerner. Death is eternal darkness, nothingness. H. Dostmuhammad approaches the problem of life and death based on Eastern philosophy. To a certain extent, it relies on the teachings of Sufism. For example, the name Zahid is also Sufi, the first Sufis were called ascetics. Zahid Yaqin repeats again and again that his soul is getting more refreshed as he approaches death and that a joy is emerging in his heart.

Adib artistically explains that the meaning of life is not in being a slave to the charms of the material world, but in goodness and faith. In a word, it revives the oriental philosophy of life in a modern form. It achieves an original interpretation for modern Uzbek literature of the 20th century.

Many literary critics see nationality in fiction, see it in customs, national dress, activities, efforts, and speech, and find its embodiment in these cases. True, these circumstances are factors that determine nationality. But it cannot be said that these tools and factors fully represent the nationality. Because these are outward manifestations of nationality. As you know, appearance is form. And the form never determines the essence of the matter. It is a means of identification. Nationalism, first of all, finds its embodiment in the psyche. All other characteristics that determine nationality depend on it, and derive from it. Spirit is the divine power, spiritual food that determines the nature and identity of a person. A strong-minded person does not give up his image, his path, i.e. the

right path, and does not give up his beliefs. In this regard, it is said in the Holy Qur'an: "They will ask you about the soul." Say, the soul is the work of Allah, and you have been given only a little knowledge. (Surah Al-Isra, verse 85), So, the soul is kneaded by knowledge, it receives nourishment from it. Its place in the human body, that is, in its nature, depends on the environment. The earlier it is enjoyed, the stronger the national character will be. In this, the role of mother and her god is great. It is a fact that does not require proof that a person who has not heard his mother's words, who is not an adult in the environment of his nation, does not have a sense of nationalism. The characteristics of the nation, which are noted in many sources, are emphasized, that is, the superiority of the spirit of living as a community; the superiority of the concepts of family, neighborhood, country; parents, neighborhood; strength of high regard for the community in general; love for the mother tongue, respect for the elder and honor for the younger, respect for women, patience and hard work, honesty, kindness. All these features are a product of the national psyche. Because these human qualities do not come from the human body, but from the feelings. The hero of the literature of the independence period has this characteristic. Rather, it is introducing these characteristics of the nation to the world through its development.

One such work is the story "Mahzuna" by Khurshid Dostmuhammad. In the story, the family is considered sacred, not to be infected, to realize that it is a woman's duty, to feel it from the inside, as well as to consider some "cultural" situations that came from Europe as foreign to the national spirit.

Both before and after getting married, Makhzuna was not among "modern women", that is, those who chow down on men, deal with them rudely, and laugh at the top of their voices. He cannot mentally digest such a situation. Her husband, Maqsadjon, was often involved in such circles, but he did not go. But this time, Maqsadjon insists that "... no, everyone comes with their wives and husbands, it will be a shame if I kiss alone."

When he comes to hospitality, he feels very uncomfortable. Especially the eyes of her husband's leader, Bori Sobitovich, seem to pierce her whole body. It also encourages you to drink as if you haven't already. Especially when his hospitality is over, putting on his coat in the hall completes Mahzuna's ado. In this regard, the author writes: "... Mahzuna felt a sting on her left shoulder, before she could put on her coat, she heard two hands squeeze her shoulders, and when she applied paint, her mouth, which was spewing smoke, came close to her cheek like a tekku and said, "Let's call"... Mahzuna the ghost of death

standing behind him like a rock, he relaxed at first as if he knew in advance that he would begin to strangle him with his cold fingers and resigned to fate. The coat on him was alive, and his limbs were lifeless. This state did not leave him even after he came home. He felt uncomfortable, as if something slimy had stuck to his body. He went to the bath and washed for a long time, "ashamed to look at the water shining like mercury in the light of the lamp, the white bath, the white wall and his white body, he snorted while pressing his palms to his face." Because Mahzuna felt as if her body was defiled and humiliated by that angry look. When he got out of the bath, his spirit was relieved. But the word "we will call" began to haunt him. Then, when Maqsadjon went on a business trip, he did not pick up the ringing phone for a day. And finally, her daughter's "Ada! Man!" - after his request, when he picked up, it was his mother who called. "Oh, my daughter, my liver is bursting!!" - he snorted at his words.

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